

ISic0183

I.Sicily inscription 0183

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance

Found outside the city gates of Termini Imerese (together with ISic1143) in 1824

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico Baldassare Romano, inventory 100

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 22 cm

Width 29 cm

Depth 11.5 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. M(arcus) Hortes[ius]

2. Primus

3. vix(it) an(nis) [V]

Apparatus

Text after ILTermini

Mommsen was able to read part of the final V

Translation (en)

Marcus Hortesius Primus, lived for 5 years

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285257

EDR 127472

EDCS 22100114

Bibliography

- Crispi, Giuseppe 1824. Spiegazione di due iscrizioni trovate nella citta di Termini. *Giornale di scienze, letteratura ed arti per la Sicilia*. 7: 82-84. At 82 no.2
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- Bivona, L. 1994. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese. *Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica*. Palermo / Rome. At 105

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